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Research Article

**ANTIBIOTIC SUSCEPTIBILITY PATTERN OF ESCHERICHIA
COLI ISOLATED FROM URINE SAMPLES OF URINARY
TRACT INFECTION PATIENTS****Muhammad Owais¹, Aman Ullah², Muhammad Umar Nafees³, Fazal Rahim⁴, Muhammad
Asif Zeb⁵, Zubair Hussain⁶, Abdul Malik⁷, Shah Faisal Jamal⁸**^{1-5,8}Institute of Paramedical Sciences, Khyber Medical University, Peshawar, Pakistan.^{6,7}National Institute of Health and Management Sciences, Peshawar, Pakistan.**Abstract:****Background:**

Objective: To determine the antibiotic sensitivity pattern against Escherichia Coli in urine of urinary tract infection patients at Peshawar, Pakistan.

Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to determine the antibiotic susceptibility pattern against Escherichia coli at Peshawar. A total of 147 non-repetitive E. coli strains isolated from urine, were studied in this study. The antibiotic susceptibility pattern was determined by Kirby Bauer method, according to guidelines of Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute, USA. Sixteen different common antibiotics were tested against E. coli.

Results: Out of total strains, 141 (95.91%) were sensitivity against Imipenem (10 µg) and 6 (4.45%) were sensitive against Nalidixic acid (30 µg). These are the highest and lowest sensitivity, recorded against E. coli. The sensitivity recorded against other antibiotics in percentage were 6.81% for Ampicillin (10 µg), 8.17% for Ticarcillin-Clavulanic acid (75/10 µg), 9.53% for Amoxycillin-Clavulanic acid (20/10 µg), 15.64% for Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole (1.24/23.75 µg), 15.64% for Cefotaxime (30 µg), 17.01% for Aztreonam (30 µg), 17.01% for Ciprofloxacin (5 µg), 17.01% for Trimethoprim (5 µg), 18.37% for Cefixime (5 µg), 19.05% for Ceftazidime (30 µg), 22.44% for Doxycycline (30 µg), 35.34% for Cefepime (30 µg), 59.18% for Nafcillin (1 µg) and 78.24% for Amikacin (30 µg).

Conclusion: We concluded from this study that only Imipenem and Amikacin were the most sensitive anti-microbial agents. The sensitivity against Nafcillin and Amikacin was not significant, as compare to Imipenem.

Key Words: Antibiotic sensitivity pattern. Escherichia coli. Urinary tract infection. Urine. Peshawar.

Corresponding author:**Muhammad Owais,**

Institute of Paramedical Sciences.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Escherichia coli (E. coli) among all microorganisms are a frequently studied bacterium. It is the most common causative agent of infectious diseases in human (1). It occurs in human and animal as commensal mostly in lower gastrointestinal tract. It causes urinary tract infection (UTI), peritonitis, hemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS), colitis, bacteremia, neonatal meningitis, diarrhea (2). Uropathogenic E. coli (UPEC) is one of the strain of E. coli, causes more than 90% of urinary tract infections (3). Other pathogenic bacteria like Proteus, Enterobacter and Klebsiella species can also cause UTI but, E. coli is the major causative agent (4).

Urinary tract infection is a life-threatening infection worldwide. Globally, the number of cases is about 150 million per year. In USA 40,000 people died per year due to UTI (5). In United states, it occur at the rate of 7.25 million cases per year (6) while, in Europeans countries the infection rate is 31.2% in 2010 and 22.3% in 2013 (3). Urinary tract infection is also prevalent in Pakistan and cause serious complication. A study conducted in 2015 in Karachi the prevalence of UTI was 47.7% (83/147) (7). Another study conducted in Peshawar reported the prevalence of UTIs due to E. coli is 39.9% (8).

In United States, a study was performed during a period of seven-years which reveals the change in susceptibility pattern of Ampicillin (61.8 to 63.2%), SXT (83.1 to 85.2%), ciprofloxacin (97.4 to 99.3%), nitrofurantoin (98.3 to 99.1%) (9). In 2015, a study conducted in 35 different hospital of UK shows the sensitivity pattern for Ceftaroline (CLSI) 89.6%, Ceftaroline (BSAC) 89.6%, Ampicillin 38.4%, Ciprofloxacin 88.0%, Cefotaxime 94.4%, Gentamicin 91.2% and Co-amoxiclav 73.6% (10). Resistance rates for Ampicillin (32.5%), Nitrofurantoin (47.5%), Gentamicin (30%), Amikacin (45%), Ciprofloxacin (35%), Augmentin (22.5%), Imipenem (67.5%) and Tazocin (87.5%) were observed (11). In Pakistan, Anwar et al., revealed sensitivity to Ceftriaxone 25%, Ceftazidime 33.3%, Cefepime 91.7%, Meropenem 50%, and Ciprofloxacin 12.5%, Augmentin 50% and Levofloxacin 62.5% (12).

According to World Health Organization (WHO), for standard antibiotic policy and treatment it is necessary that there should be a recent published report of antibiotic sensitivity pattern. According to these guidelines, the susceptibility pattern of the

antibiotic should not be older than three months. As the susceptibility of pathogens is changing with time due to continues mutation. Therefore, this study was conducted at Peshawar to determine the pattern of antibiotic susceptibility in this region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at Sina labs, Hayatabad, Peshawar. A total of 147 non-repetitive strains of E. coli were included in this study, which was isolated from urine. Sensitivity pattern was determined by disc diffusion method, according to the guidelines (CLSI M100 28th edition) of Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute (CLSI), USA(13). Sixteen different antibiotics were used in different concentrations against E. coli. Then the isolates were refreshed by using selective medium, cysteine lactose and electrolyte-deficient (CLED) agar. After refreshing, E. coli was confirmed by various tests, i.e. morphology of the colonies, Sulfide Indole Motility (SIM) test, triple sugar iron (TSI) test and catalase test. All E. coli sample were positive for indole production and motility, but negative for H₂S reduction.

After identification, the samples were processed for antibiotic sensitivity test (AST) against Amikacin (AK) 30 µg, Aztreonam (ATM) 30 µg, Ampicillin (AMP) 10 µg, Ciprofloxacin (CIP) 5 µg, Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole (SXT) 1.24/23.75 µg, Trimethoprim (W) 5 µg, Doxycycline (DO) 30 µg, Ceftazidime (CAZ) 30 µg, Cefixime (CFM) 5 µg, Cefotaxime (CTX) 30 µg, Cefepime (FEP) 30 µg, Amoxicillin-Clavulanic acid (AMC) 20/10 µg, Nalidixic acid (NA) 30 µg, Nafcillin (NF) 1 µg, Ticarcillin-Clavulanic acid (TIM) 75/10 µg and Imipenem (IPM) 10 µg. The inoculated plates were incubated at 36°C for 24 hours. On next day the zone of inhibition was measured from one edge of inhibition area to other including disk area. This area was measured at the bottom side of plates by keeping the lids of plate closed. Then the recorded diameter was matched with the CLSI chart and the E. coli strains are categorized as sensitive and resistant.

RESULT:

A total of 147 positive samples of E. coli were tested against sixteen antibiotics. Out of 147 strains, 141 (95.91%) were sensitive against Imipenem, showing the highest sensitivity followed by Amikacin 78.24% and Nafcillin 59.18%. While Nalidixic Acid had the lowest sensitivity 6 (4.45%) followed by Ampicillin 6.8, Ticarcillin- Clavulanic Acid 8.16% and Amoxicillin-Clavulanic Acid 9.52% (table 1).

Table-I: Antibiotic susceptibility pattern of E. coli.

S. No	ANTIBIOTIC	SENSITIVE		RESISTANT		TOTAL
		No. of E. coli	Percentage	No. of E. coli	Percentage	
1	Amikacin (AK) 30 µg	115	78.24	32	21.76	147
2	Aztreonam (ATM) 30 µg	25	17.01	122	82.99	147
3	Ampicillin (AMP) 10 µg	10	6.80	137	93.20	147
4	Ciprofloxacin (CIP) 5 µg	25	17.01	122	82.99	147
5	Co-trimoxazole (SXT) 1.24/23.75 µg	23	15.64	124	84.36	147
6	Trimethoprim (W) 5 µg	25	17.01	122	82.99	147
7	Doxycycline (Do) 30 µg	33	22.44	114	77.56	147
8	Ceftazidime (CAZ) 30 µg	28	19.04	119	80.96	147
9	Cefixime (CFM) 5 µg	27	18.36	120	81.64	147
10	Cefotaxime (CTX) 30 µg	23	15.64	124	84.36	147
11	Cefepime (FEP) 30 µg	52	35.34	92	64.66	147
12	Amoxicillin - Clavulanic Acid (AMC) 20/10 µg	14	9.52	133	90.48	147
13	Nalidixic Acid (NA) 30 µg	8	4.45	139	95.55	147
14	Nafcillin (NF) 1 µg	87	59.18	60	40.82	147
15	Ticarcillin - Clavulanic Acid (TIM) 75/10 µg	12	8.16	135	91.84	147
16	Imipenem (IPM) 10 µg	141	95.91	6	04.09	147

DISCUSSION:

In Pakistan, urinary tract infection is a noteworthy health issue. Mostly, infants and young children

suffer from this infection. After respiratory infection, UTI is the second most occurring infection in children (7).

This recent study revealed that the highest sensitivity was 59.18% for Nafcillin (1 µg). 78.24% for Amikacin (30 µg) and 95.91% for Imipenem (10 µg).

In 2013 at tertiary care hospital at Peshawar, Pakistan a study was conducted which shows the sensitivity pattern for Co-amoxiclav 82.14%, Ampicillin 21.43%, Cefuroxime 46.43%, Nalidixic Acid 25%, Co-trimoxazole 35.71%, Cefixime 53.57%, Cefotaxime 50%, Amikacin 100% and Aztreonam 57.14% (14). Compared to this report, the present study has same result for Co-amoxiclav, Ampicillin, Nalidixic acid and Co-trimoxazole, but sensitivity of Amikacin is slightly decreased because of its widespread use.

Same kind of study done in 2015, at Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar, shows highest sensitivity to Imipenem and Amikacin, having values of 98.6% and 92.5% respectively. But sensitivity was less significant to Nalidixic acid, Ampicillin, Ofloxacin, Norfloxacin and Enoxacin (15). A study processed at Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar, published in 2017, shows that Sulzone, Imipenem and Meronem are 100% sensitive and amikacin 93.4% (16). By comparing these reports to the recent study, the resistance against ampicillin and nalidixic acid has the same pattern but, sensitivity against Imipenem and Amikacin is decreases. Decreases in sensitivity occur due to self-medication and transfer of resistant strains from animals.

A study conducted in 2017, at Hayatabad Medical Complex Peshawar, shows sensitivity for Ceftriaxone (53.2%), Ciprofloxacin (54.5%), Amoxicillin/Clavulanate (63.6%), Ampicillin (61%), Erythromycin (55.8%), Nitrofurantoin (46.8%) (8). In comparison to this study, sensitivity to Ciprofloxacin, Ampicillin and Amoxicillin/Clavulanate is decreased and become fully resistant. The sensitive strains become resistant due to over use of antibiotics, poor infection control, poor hygiene system and not finishing whole antibiotic course.

One of the strength of our study is that some antibiotic which were not used in the previous studies had a high sensitivity pattern i.e. Nafcillin 59.18%. While antibiotics, Cefepime, Ticarcillin-Clavulanic acid were found resistant to E. coli which were not reported in the previous studies.

CONCLUSION:

Conclusively we determined that Amikacin, imipenem had high susceptibility pattern followed by Nafcillin. While other antibiotics had low sensitivity

indicating that the susceptibility pattern is changing. Therefore, it is recommended to conduct further studies to determine the reason of increase resistance to antibiotic against E.coli.

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